

Science

THE RELATION OF INTERIOR SPACES WITH URBAN CONTEXT

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Abstract

Space, it is the area provided for particular purpose. Space can be two dimensional, three dimensional or multi. The perception of a space is known by its functionality and quality. Space does not define the use or behavior. Space can be identified as interior, exterior, common, transition; public, personal etc. 90 percent of our daily lives are spent inside. That is our experience of the city – moving from one interior to another. So our remit is to improve the quality of life for citizen, focusing on the quality of interior spaces.

Keywords: Relation; Interior Spaces; Urban Context.

Cite This Article: Ar. Tulsi N. Patel. (2018). “THE RELATION OF INTERIOR SPACES WITH URBAN CONTEXT.” *International Journal of Research - Granthaalayah*, 6(2), 162-165. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1189227>.

1. Introduction

Space, it is the area provided for particular purpose. Space can be two dimensional, three dimensional or multi. The perception of a space is known by its functionality and quality. Space does not define the use or behavior. Space can be identified as interior, exterior, common, transition; public, personal etc. 90 percent of our daily lives are spent inside. That is our experience of the city – moving from one interior to another. So our remit is to improve the quality of life for citizen, focusing on the quality of interior spaces.

Urban thinker Kevin Lynch was able to establish a notation of city elements that matched people’s perception. They are identified as District, Paths, Edges, Nodes, and Landmarks. Nodes, paths thus, the similar type of urban elements can be seen in smaller scales with in a building. Through his book “IMAGE OF THE CITY” Kevin Lynch explained that people orient themselves by means of mental maps, i.e. perception of space. A design should be in such a way that it gives room for three related movements - MAPPING, LEARNING AND SHAPING.

MAPPING: people should create or acquire a clear map of the environment. LEARNING: People should be able to learn how to navigate in the environments. SHAPING: People should be able to operate and act in the environment.

2. Kevin Lynch Five Elements

The relationships of Interior spaces are explained with the five elements of the image of the city.

2.1. Paths

The streets, sidewalks, trail and other channels in which people travel. Paths organize the mobility, the patterns of street network is what defines a city and makes it unique. They are defined by their physical dimension, size, shape and character of the buildings that live them. They range from plaza to intimate small paths.

2.1.1. Paths in Interior Spaces

In interior, paths are identifies as corridors, halls, galleries, stairways and ramps. User should be able to map out the overall configuration of the paths in the paths in the building mentally, orientation within the building and understanding of its spatial layout will be made clear within a large space, a path can be random, without form or definition and be determined by activities and arrangement of furnishing within the space. The scale of a circulation space, however, should accommodate the movement of people as they walk, pause, rest or take in a view along path.

2.2. Nodes

A common point where two or more roads meet to form a junction or square. The strategic focus points for orientations of squares and junctions. Nodes to increase the perception of an active, urban corridor and to encourage more walking. It Strengthen the emphasis on alternative mode use in the corridor. It Contribute to the overall vibrancy, safety, and desirability of the area. These nodes should occur where single uses or a combination of uses lead to higher levels of pedestrian activity. Pedestrian nodes should include such furnishings as drinking fountains, trash cans, and benches to increase the users' sense of comfort. Seating should be arranged to accommodate groups of people Careful thought should be given to the amount of seating provided because too much unused seating may detract from the goal of creating an active area.

2.2.1. Nodes in Interior Spaces

In interiors, Nodes are identified as transition spaces, intersecting spaces and common gathering spaces where people of different activities meet together while moving. These nodes punctuate the paths of movement through a building and provide opportunities for pause, rest and reorientation. These are the casual common spaces with an unstructured environment that promotes comfort and relaxation. Persons approaching an intersection or crossing are always faced with a decision. To avoid the creation of a disorienting maze, a hierarchical order among the paths and nodes of a building should be established by differentiating their scale, form, length and placement.

2.3. Edges

They are boundaries between two phases, Bodies of water (such as an ocean, river, or lake) Landforms (such as mountains and hills) Manmade structures (such as buildings, railroad tracks, walls, or highways) The Functionality and usage of the spaces are clearly defined by edges. The characteristics of Edges act in a space by stopping it, more or less penetrable, or they may be seams, lines along which two regions are related and joined together. Street edges need to be oriented and/or adjusted for maximum light on the space between buildings, and not just for interior penetration, in order to encourage active street life. Edges that are seen from building to street.

2.3.1. Edges in Interior Spaces

We view site and building as a series of free-flowing interior and exterior space. colonnades, courtyards, windows and trellises are transparent barriers, where public meets private, indoors meets outdoors, light meets shadow; places of crossing over. Within a room edges can be defined as separating planes like partition walls, curtains, furniture, grills etc. It allows each space to be clearly defined and respond in its own way. It creates adjacency the most common spatial relationship. Views and vistas become an integral part of interior spaces. Edges should act as both separator and connector in a space. The degree of spatial continuity that occurs between two spaces will depends on the nature of plane that both separates and bind together. Edges are also created by using jails, as semi separators, screens which gives partial privacy.

2.4. Districts

Areas characterized by common characteristics, these are the medium to large areas, which have some common identifying character. Distinctive physical characteristics might include ‘thematic continuities’, such as texture, space, form, detail, symbol, function and building.

2.4.1. Districts in Interior Spaces

In interior spaces, districts can be termed as zones that are divided for achieving the functionality and comfort of the occupant. A kitchen with its adjoining wash area, store area forms a district. The presence of these and other similar attributes reinforce a district’s fabric, cohesiveness, and identity Good planning makes for livable neighborhoods’, a safe and healthy community, and a sustainable economy. Zoning helps in creating identity to the place, security and enrich private and social behavior.

2.5. Landmarks

External points of orientation, easily identified objects – towers, spires, hills are distant and are typically seen from many angles and from distance, over the top of smaller elements. Other landmarks – sculptures, signs and trees are primarily local being visible only in restricted localities and from certain approaches. The importance is functionally prominent structures have a major influence on the aesthetics of their immediate urban landscape; location, function of

open spaces and landscape furniture. Physical characteristics are some aspect that is unique or memorable in the context.

2.5.1. Landmarks in Interior Spaces

In Interiors Landmarks are identifies variously depending on the scale and focus of the element. It can also define functionality of the space. A sculpture in the middle of lobby creates path avoiding haphazard movement acting as a memorable landmark. The scale and proportion of columns define space and also highlights the importance acting as focal point. The enhancing a architectural feature with interior color and textures allowing natural light add to the aesthetics of the place marking it as landmark or active and interesting feature. A prime functional element of circulation is enhanced by adding sculpture in design and color to it. Scale, Focus made the element of design as a landmark.

Architects are much more involved in the icon of the building envelope. What does it look like from the outside? So Interiors were marginalized into a very small field, which itself has been split between interior architecture and interior decoration. All these disciplines have really been subdivided. The result is it becomes easier to lose the bigger picture of how all these things interact.

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